

Research

A Comparative Study of Bacteriology in Recurrent Tonsillitis Among Children and Adults of Madhesh Province, Nepal with Reference to Pediatric Age Group 2 to 15 years and Adult Age Group above 15 years

Santosh Kumar Sah^{1*}, Baidhyanath Thakur¹, Sharad Yadav¹

¹Madhesh Institute of Health Sciences(MIHS), Janakpurdham, Madhesh province, Nepal

Abstract: Objective: The present study of Bacteriology was conducted to see the recurrent Tonsillitis effects on Children of 2 to 15 years and Adults of above 15 years of the Madhesh province, Nepal. Method: This is a comparative study in children of 2 to 15 years and Adult of Above 15 years. The population of the study was centered in the Madhesh Province of Nepal and the samples were collected from Schools, Villages and local health posts and district Hospitals of Madhesh province. Staphylococcus species of bacteria were found responsible for causing tonsillitis. The children were found more prone than that of adults suffering from tonsillitis. The poor families were more susceptible than the families of medium and above medium range. 130 samples were collected using structured questionnaires. SPSS was used to analyze the samples. Some of the isolation process followed by Madhesh Province Hospitals and results found there were to take decision. The study covers the period of more than 1 years. Chi-square test was used to make the valid decision. Result: Of the total 130 out of 200 patients grew single pathogenic bacteria in their tonsillar core culture, 35 different pathogenic bacteria, and the rest (35) grew normal bacterial flora. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most commonly isolated bacterium and accounted for 37 percent of the total cultures isolated; its prevalence was the same in the adults and children. -Haemolytic Streptococcus was isolated in 20 percent of subjects and was predominantly from group A (*Streptococcus pyogenes*). Group A -haemolytic Streptococci was more prevalent in children. Pseudomonas aeruginosa, which rarely causes pathogenicity in tonsils, was cultured from nine (5 percent) of our study subjects. Conclusion: *Staphylococcus aureus* is the most common pathogenic bacteria cultured both in adults and children. It may be a steppingstone to eventually understanding whether the bacteria play a role in reactivating recurrent infections. From previous and current studies, there is no relationship between bacteriology and recurrent infections. The mechanism of activation of infection in recurrent tonsillitis is unknown, knowing the bacteriology does not help us to treat the disease.

Keywords: Bacteriology, Recurrence, Tonsillitis, Tonsillectomy, Madhesh Province Nepal.

*Corresponding Author: Santosh Kumar Sah, Madhesh Institute of Health Sciences (MIHS), Janakpurdham, Madhesh province, Nepal

Accepted: 01 August, 2024; **Published:** 04 August, 2024

How to cite this article: Santosh Kumar Sah, Baidhyanath Thakur, Sharad Yadav (2024). A Comparative Study of Bacteriology in Recurrent Tonsillitis Among Children and Adults of Madhesh Province, Nepal with Reference to Pediatric Age Group 2 to 15 years and Adult Age Group above 15 years. *North American Academic Research*, 7(8), 1-9. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13218166>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) is fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

In Madhesh Province, Nepal, diagnosis and treatment of acute tonsillitis are one of the most common problems seen in both adult and pediatric populations. Much has been written about bacteriology of recurrent tonsillitis but it remains a controversial and unsolved topic. Despite the fact that tonsillitis is so common, consensus seems to be lacking as to the main causative organism and the differences between children and adults. The tonsillar core bacteriology of 200 patients with recurrent tonsillitis who underwent tonsillectomy from January 2022 to June 2023 is presented. Some of these patients will eventually undergo a tonsillectomy. Tonsillectomy is the commonest surgical procedure in children. About 400 tonsillectomies were performed per annum in the Madhesh Province. About 800,000 in the USA and about 66,350 in England. Much has been written about the bacteriology of recurrent tonsillitis but it remains a controversial topic[1].

Bacteria are single-celled microorganisms, microscopic in nature that lack a nuclear membrane, are metabolically active and divide by binary fission. Medically they are a major cause of disease. The scientific and systematic study of bacteria is called Bacteriology. A new occurrence of something that happened or appeared before, a repeated occurrence. Scientists are working to lower the disease's rate of recurrence. In our studies, recurrence means the first time happening and re-happening of the tonsillitis to the same person within a given period of time in spite of the treatments and recovery in the previous times[2].

Tonsillitis is inflammation of the tonsils, two oval-shaped pads of tissue at the back of the throat — one tonsil on each side. Signs and symptoms of tonsillitis include swollen tonsils, sore throat, difficulty swallowing and tender lymph nodes on the sides of the neck, painful in nature with light to severe fever and loss of appetite.

Tonsillectomy is the surgical removal of the tonsils, two oval-shaped pads of tissue at the back of the throat; one tonsil on each side. A tonsillectomy was once a common procedure to treat infection and inflammation of the tonsils (tonsillitis). Today, a tonsillectomy is usually performed for sleep-disordered breathing but may still be a treatment when tonsillitis occurs frequently or doesn't respond to other treatments. A tonsillectomy may also be necessary to treat breathing and other problems related to enlarged tonsils and to treat rare diseases of the tonsils. Recovery time for a tonsillectomy is usually at least 10 days to two weeks depending the weather conditions and care taken by the patients. Most cases of tonsillitis are caused by infection with a common virus, but bacterial infections are the major causes tonsillitis[3].

Nepal was a Kingdom before 1990. In 1990 there was peoples movements and Nepal was declared as Multiparty, Secular, inclusive and a Republic county and Monarchial system of 237 years was terminated. Nepal was divided into 7 provinces and 77 districts. primarily the name for provinces were given as Province No. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7. Later the names were finalized by the provincial assemblies in their own. On 17 January, the provincial assembly of Province 2 in Nepal with over two-thirds majority named Province 2 as Madhesh Pradesh with its capital in Janakpur. Of the total 99 provincial assembly members who cast their votes on that day, 78 voted in favour of Janakpur as the capital; whereas 80 voted for Madhesh as the name of this province. Under the federal democratic republic Constitution of Nepal, promulgated in September 2015, this province was given a numerical name as Province 2 with its temporary capital in Janakpur. As per the Nepalese Constitution, each province in the federal structure was free to choose its name as well as its capital if it was endorsed by at least two-thirds majority of their respective provincial assemblies. Accordingly, all the five provinces, including Province 3, Province 4, Province 5, Province 6, and Province 7 were successfully given names. Province 1 is yet to be named, and it was also lately finalized as Koshi Pradesh. The

decision made by the provincial assembly members of Province 2 to name it 'Madhesh Pradesh' is applauded most by the people[4].

Organisms grown from superficial swabs may not be the same as those obtained from the tonsillar core, and there is almost certainly a difference between children and adults. Throat swabs have little value in the diagnosis of the causative organism compared to deep tissue culture in recurrent tonsillitis. There is strong anatomical evidence for the presence of bacterial presence to occur tonsillitis.

Research Methodology

The patient population was divided into two groups, namely: the pediatric group (of age class range of 2 to 15 years and adults of more than 15 years.130 patients, whose age was more than 15 years, were in the adult group. 76 patients aged between 2 and 15 years, were in the pediatric group. 54 were adult group. The bacteriology of the children and adults were tabulated according to their species, and were compared.

This is a non-randomized, purposive sampling was done. A prospective study held over 1 year (January 2022 to June, 2023). Patients were selected from those who were going for tonsillectomy and for treatment of Tonsillitis local hospitals and government health centers.. They were divided into two groups, namely: the pediatric group (patients from two to 15 years old) and the adult group (patients older than 15 years old). Inclusion criteria were: three or more severe recurrent attacks of tonsillitis in two consecutive years. High fever, snoring during acute attacks, unable to take normal diet, absence from school/work, and admission to hospital, are present.

Research Objectives-

- To make a comparative study of different organisms causing Tonsillitis in adults and children of the Madhesh Province.
- To see the impact of Tonsillectomy in the patients.

A descriptive and an analytical method was used. Samples were collected from different local hospitals of the Madhesh Province and laboratories working in Tonsillitis. 130 samples were considered for the research purpose. Data were mostly of secondary nature with some of the primary source of data. Total count, percentages and Chi-Square test were conducted to make valid decision.

Results

Staphylococcus aureus was the most commonly-isolated bacterium and accounted for 37 percent of the total cultures isolated. out of 200 Patients, 130 patients grew single pathogenic bacteria in their tonsillar core culture, 35 grew two different pathogenic bacteria, and the rest (35) grew normal bacterial flora and its prevalence was the same in the adults and children. -Haemolytic Streptococcus was isolated in 20 percent of subjects, and was predominantly from group A (Streptococcus pyogenes). Group A -haemolytic Streptococci was more prevalent in children. Pseudomonas aeruginosa, which rarely cause pathogenicity in tonsils, was cultured from nine (5 percent) of our study subjects.

Among the below tabulated details of the Patients who satisfied the criteria by history and clinical examination were subjected to Patients who satisfied the criteria by history and clinical examination were subjected to tonsillectomy. Tonsillectomy for all these patients were carried out by the blunt dissection method. All the tonsils were cut into two halves. One-half from each side was sent for histopathology and the other half for core culture. The histopathology was reviewed, and patients who did not have evidence of chronic infection were further excluded. Based on the above criteria, 200 patients were included in this study, out of whom 83 were adults and 117 were children. The bacteriology of the children and adults were tabulated according to their species, and were compared. This part was taken from hospital pathology unit. From the 35 patients in whom a mixed culture was isolated, more than one organism

was isolated from each patient which occurred in different permutations and combinations. But the type of organisms and its prevalence in adults and children were similar to that of the single culture.

Table1: Types of cultures isolated in adults and children and their distribution

Age Category	Single	Mix	Flora	Total
Adult	54	15	14	83
Child	76	20	21	117
Total	130(65%)	35(17.5%)	35 (17.5%)	200 (100%)

From the below table , 130 patients in whom a single organism was isolated, *Staphylococcus aureus* was predominantly seen in adults (44 %); and the was predominantly seen in children (42%). *Klebsiella pneumonia* (28.0%) was the next most common organism in adults, and in children (26.32%) . The other organisms isolated in the single culture were Haemophilus influenza, Streptococcus pneumonia, Pseudomonas, Enterobacter, Escherichia coli and Acinetobacter. First of all an attempt was made to compare the various organisms isolated in the single culture group for adults and children . The following table describes the details of the causal organism.

Table 2: Comparison of various organisms isolated in the single culture group

Organisms	Adult		Children		Total	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Staphylococcus aureus	24	44	32	42.10	56	43.10
Klebsiella pneumonia	15	28	20	26.32	35	26.92
β-haemolytic Streptococcus	6	11	8	10.53	14	10.79
Haemophilus influenza	1	1.89	2	2.63	3	2.30
Streptococcus pneumonia	3	5.79	5	6.58	8	6.75
Pseudomonas	1	1.85	2	2.63	3	2.30
Enterobacter	1	1.85	2	2.63	3	2.30
Escherichia coli	1	1.85	2	2.63	3	2.30
Acinetobacter	2	3.77	3	3.95	5	3.54
Total	54	100	76	100	130	100

The below table describes that the *Staphylococcus aureus* was the main causal organism to cause Tonsillitis. It was 26 % and 28% in adults and children respectively. *Klebsiella pneumonia* was the second in order to cause Tonsillitis in adults and children and their density to cause was 13 % and 14% respectively. β-haemolytic Streptococcus was also active to act as a causal organism. Acinetobacter was least active in causing Tonsillitis in Madhesh Province.

To make the comparison of various organisms isolated in the mixed groups of adults and Children, the following table was framed.

Table 3: Comparison of various organisms isolated in the mixed group.

Organisms	Adult		Children		Total	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Staphylococcus aureus	14	26	21	28	35	27
Klebsiella pneumonia	7	13	11	14	18	14
β-haemolytic Streptococcus	7	13	9	11.64	16	12
Haemophilus influenza	4	7	9	11.64	13	10

Streptococcus pneumonia	7	13	7	9.20	14	11
Pseudomonas	5	9	8	11	13	10
Enterobacter	4	7	7	9.20	11	8
Escherichia coli	4	7	3	4	7	5
Acinetobacter	2	5	1	1.32	3	3
Total	54	100	76	100	130	100

From the total organisms cultured from single and mixed cultures of table 1 and 3 , the commonly isolated organisms from adults were *Staphylococcus aureus* (37%), *Klebsiella pneumonia* (15 %) and -haemolytic Streptococcus (20 %); while in children, *Staphylococcus aureus* (37%), -haemolytic Streptococcus (15 %) and Haemophilus influenza (6 %) . *Klebsiella pneumonia*, Streptococcus pneumonia and Enterobacter were more prevalent in adults; while -haemolytic Streptococcus and Haemophilus influenza were more prevalent in children. Streptococcus pneumonia was isolated from ten patients (9 %), out of which nine are from adults. Escherichia coli was isolated from four of the tonsillar cores of adults but none from the paediatric age group. Pseudomonas aeruginosa was seen in ten patients, out of which a single organism was cultured in four of the patients; the incidence is the same in both adults and children. The overall comparison was also made to study various types of organisms between adults and children. The following table No.4 describes in details about the comparison.

Table 4: An overall comparison of various types of organisms between adults and children.

Organisms:	Adult		Children		Total	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
Staphylococcus aureus	32	38	42	37	74	37
Klebsiella pneumonia	11	14	18	15	29	15
β-haemolytic Streptococcus	17	20	23	20	40	20
Haemophilus influenza	5	6	7	6	12	6
Streptococcus pneumonia	7	8	11	9	18	9
Pseudomonas	4	5	6	5	10	5
Enterobacter	3	4	4	3	7	3
Escherichia coli	3	4	4	3	7	3
Acinetobacter	1	1	2	2	3	2
Total	83	100	117	100	200	100

As seen in Table 5 Haemolytic Streptococcus, including from Group A and C, was found in tonsillar cores of 35 (100 %) cultures. Predominantly Group B was isolated in 46% of the cultures and it was found to be prevalent in children. Group A was prevalent in Adult , i.e. 26 % .

Table 5: Presence of Different types of Hemolytic Streptococcus bacterium in Adults and Children of Madhesh Province of Nepal

Beta H.S.	Adults	Children	Total
Group A (Pyogens)	2 (13%)	3(15 %)	5 (14 %)
Group A	4(26 %)	5 (25 %)	9 (26 %)
Group B	7(48 %)	9 (45 %)	16 (46 %)
Group C	2(13%)	3 (15 %)	5 (14 %)

Total	15(100 %)	20 (100 %)	35 (100 %)
-------	------------	-------------	------------

Another attempt was also made to see the success (positive effect of Tonsillectomy) in the patients. Another report was also received from one of the Hospitals of the Madhesh Province and a Chi-square Test was conducted. A total of 500 patients' records were taken and the test was conducted as -

Hypothesis-

H0: Tonsillectomy is not effective

H1: Tonsillectomy is effective

Table 6: Comparison of tonsillectomy and non tonsillectomy effects.

Reoccured/Tonsillectomy done	Tonsillectomy done	Tonsillectomy not done	Total
Reoccured	72	128	200
Not reoccured	102	198	300
Grand Total	174	326	500

Again,

Observed (O)	Expected (E)	(O- E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
72	70	2	4	0.0571
128	130	-2	4	0.0307
102	104	-2	4	0.0384
198	195	3	9	0.0461
Total	500	499		0.1723

Tabulated value at (r-1)(c-1) and 1 d.f. 3.841 whereas calculated Chi-Square value is 0.1723 which is less than tabulated Value. So test is insignificant and H0 is accepted i. e. Tonsillectomy is not effective in controlling Tonsillitis and so, it is reoccurring in the patients of Madhesh Province of Nepal.

Discussion

In their study in 1991, Gaffney et al[5] found that Haemophilus influenza was the single most common bacterium isolated from the centre of the tonsil (referred to as the tonsil core), and this was more prevalent in children. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the next most commonly isolated bacterium. Mixed pathogens were found throughout all age groups and -Haemolytic Streptococcus from Group A to G were found in 22%, out of which 62% was from Group A. Bacteriology of the tonsillar core may change with age, and it was found that -haemolytic Streptococci was more common in children than in adults[13-15]. The incidence of -Haemolytic Streptococcus Group A variety was the most prevalent group, followed by Group C. Danielides et al[17] reported a case of recurrent tonsillitis caused by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* which they found to be rare. Anaerobic bacteria were present in a significant number of acutely inflamed tonsils, compared to healthy children[18,19]. In 132 adults and 101 children in which the core tonsillar bacteriology was studied, mixed pathogens were seen in 22.2% of patients, predominantly in adults (13.7%). Gaffney et al[5] observed similar findings. Predominantly *Staphylococcus aureus* was cultured in both adults and children with an almost equal incidence. Brook et al[20] observed a similar prevalence. In adults, the next common organisms were *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Streptococcus haemolytic*, *Streptococcus pneumonia* and Haemophilus influenza; while in children, the

next common organisms were -haemolytic Streptococcus followed by Haemophilus influenza and Klebsiella pneumonia. *Klebsiella pneumonia* was isolated from 22.1% of adult cultures. Previous publications in the literature of core cultures do not report the significance of *Klebsiella pneumonia* in their studies. The prevalence of *Klebsiella pneumonia* is low (5.0%) in children compared to adults. Haemophilus influenza was found only in 10.0% of total cultured organisms, compared to other studies by Gaffney et al[5], Surow et al[21] and Lidroos[22]. They found that Haemophilus influenza was the most common organism cultured, followed by Staphylococcus aureus. Gaffney et al[5] isolated Haemophilus influenza from 72% of core culture samples; however, the prevalence of Haemophilus influenza according to age group was similar to this study. Haemolytic Streptococcus was the second most common organism isolated from children and was more prevalent, compared to adults. The prevalence of Group A -haemolytic Streptococcus (*Streptococcus pyogenes*) was similar to the studies by Brook and Foote[14], and Ramirez et al[16]. Unlike this study, Gaffney et al[5] found Group A -haemolytic Streptococcus to be more prevalent in adults. The prevalence of Group B, Group C and Group G -haemolytic Streptococcus differed in all previous studies, which we feel may represent a geographical difference[5,14]. *Klebsiella pneumonia* and *Escherichia coli* were seen more commonly in adults compared to children. This may be due to transient colonisation of these organisms in adults secondary to repeated use of antibiotics[23]. *Klebsiella pneumonia* was more common than Haemophilus influenza, compared to previous studies[5,21,22]; the difference may be due to a wider use of antimicrobials in this region and the multi-resistant characteristic of *Klebsiella pneumonia* compared to Haemophilus influenza[24]. This may bring about colonisation of these resistant organisms, giving rise to recurrent infections. A comparative study of the histology of tonsils between recurrent tonsillitis and tonsillar hypertrophy by Zhang et al showed that reactive lymphoid hyperplasia and presence of chronic inflammatory cells, predominantly lymphocytes, are the two most important features that is seen in patients with recurrent tonsillitis. The part played by viruses in acute tonsillitis is unknown, and in children, it has been felt that an initial viral tonsillitis may predispose to a super infection by bacteria[1]. The composition of normal commensal bacteria of oropharynx and nose, i.e. Viridans streptococci, Bacteroids, Fusobacteria, Spirochaetes, Lactobacilli, Veillonella and other anaerobic cocci, Actinomyces, Haemophilus influenzae, Streptococcus pneumoniae, Staphylococcus epidermidis, Staphylococcus aureus, and coliforms, such as *Escherichia coli*, Proteus, Klebsiella and Pseudomonas, may be disrupted by frequent use of broad-spectrum antimicrobials, by inhibiting sensitive organisms and allowing overgrowth of the resistant ones. This may cause serious infection by the normal commensally. Despite the fact that tonsillitis is so common, consensus seems to be lacking as to the main causative organisms and its differences in children and adults. Streptococcus pneumonia was found in ten patients, out of which nine were from adults, compared to Gaffney et al[5] who reported a higher prevalence in children. The incidence of recurrent tonsillitis secondary to Pseudomonas was not rare in our study compared to previous papers[5,14,17]. 18% of the patients did not grow any pathogenic organisms even though the histopathological criteria were observed in the inclusion criteria. The histopathological criteria for chronic bacterial tonsillitis thus showed a significant false positivity. This may be due to the shortcomings of this study whereby no anaerobic cultures were done in all the core tissue samples, due to the difficulties and errors arising from delay in delivery time, exposure of sample to air and longer culture time. However, Gaffney et al[5] found that strict anaerobic species were isolated in significant numbers from the tonsil core in 5% out of 120 patients, but were present in superficial culture in all. Anaerobes were present in moderate to heavy numbers in

32% of superficial swabs overall and this was more frequently seen in older age groups. In conclusion, we feel that more studies are needed in a better-controlled environment to understand the bacteriology of recurrent tonsillitis.

Conclusion

This study conducted in the Madhesh Province of Nepal clearly showed that *Staphylococcus aureus* is the most common pathogenic bacteria cultured both in adults and children. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacter* are more prevalent in adults. *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Streptococcus* pathogens are more prevalent in children. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is not a rare causative organism in recurrent tonsillitis. Since the mechanism of activation of infection in recurrent tonsillitis is unknown, knowing the bacteriology does not help us to treat the disease. However, it may be a stepping stone to eventually understanding whether the bacteria play a role in reactivating recurrent infections. From previous and current studies, there is no relationship between bacteriology and recurrent infections.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Jha, H. B. (2022). The new name of Madhesh province surprises Nepal. Retrieved from Observer Research Foundation: <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/new-name-of-madhesh-province-surprises-nepal>
- Staff, M. C. (2022). Tonsillitis. Retrieved from Mayo Clinic: <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/tonsillitis/symptoms-causes/syc-20378479>
- Palumbo FM. Pediatric considerations of infections and inflammations of Waldeyer's ring. *Otolaryngol Clin North Am* 1987; 20:311-6.
- Barr G. Further thoughts about tonsillectomy. *Ir Med J* 1989; 82:142. 3
- Cowan DL, Hibbert J. *Scott-Brown's Otolaryngology*. Vol 5. 6th ed. London: Butterworth Heinemann, 1997:2.
- Ylikoski J, Karjalainen J. Acute tonsillitis in young men: etiological agents and their differentiation. *Scand J Infect Dis* 1989; 21:169-74.
- Gaffney RJ, Freeman DJ, Walsh MA, et al. Differences in tonsil core bacteriology in adults and children: a prospective study of 262 patients. *Resp Med* 1991; 85:383-8.
- Robinson AC, Hanif J, Dumbreck LA, et al. Throat swabs in chronic tonsillitis: a time-honoured practice best forgotten. *Br J Clin Pract* 1997; 51:138-9.
- Brodsky L, Nagy M, Volk M, et al. The relationship of tonsil bacterial concentration to surface and core cultures in chronic tonsillar disease in children. *Int J Paed Otolaryngol* 1991; 21:33-9.
- Kurien M, Stanis A, Job A, et al. Throat swab in the chronic tonsillitis: how reliable and valid is it? *Singapore Med J* 2000; 41:324-6.
- Chole RA, Faddis BT. Anatomical evidence of microbial biofilms in tonsillar tissues: a possible mechanism to explain chronicity. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2003; 129:634-6.
- Osterlund A, Popa R, Nikkila T, et al. Intracellular reservoir of *Streptococcus pyogenes* in vivo: a possible explanation for recurrent pharyngotonsillitis. *Laryngoscope* 1997; 107:640-7.
- Zhang PC, Pang YT, Loh KS, et al. Comparison of histology between recurrent tonsillitis and tonsillar hypertrophy. *Clin Otolaryngol* 2003; 28:235-9.
- Everett, M. T. The cause of tonsillitis. *Practitioner* 1979; 223:253-259.

15. Polvogt LM, Crowe SJ. Predominating organisms found in cultures from tonsils and adenoids. *J Am Med Assoc* 1929; 92:962-4.
16. Brook I, Foote P. Comparison of the microbiology of recurrent tonsillitis between children and adults. *Laryngoscope* 1986; 96:1385-7.
17. Nandi S, Kumar R, Ray P, et al. Clinical score card for diagnosis of Group A streptococcal sore throat. *Indian J Paediatr* 2002; 69:471-5
18. Reilly S, Timmis P, Beeden AG, et al. Possible role of the anaerobe in tonsillitis. *J Clin Pathol* 1981; 34:542-7.
19. Darrow DH, Siemens C. Indications for tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy. *Laryngoscope* 2002; 112(8 Pt 2 Suppl 100):6-10.
20. Brook I, Yocum P, Foote P. Changes in the tonsillar bacteriology of recurrent tonsillitis: 1977-1993. *Clin Infect Dis* 1995; 21:171-6.
21. Sarrow JB, Handler SD, Telian SA, et al. Bacteriology of tonsil surface and core in children. *Laryngoscope* 1989; 99:261-6.
22. Lidroos R. Bacteriology of the tonsil core in recurrent tonsillitis and tonsillar hyperplasia – a short review. *Acta Otolaryngol Suppl* 2000; 543:206-8.
23. Sleight JD, Timbury MC. *Medical Bacteriology*. 4th ed. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone, 1994:197.
24. Sharma R, Sharma CL, Kapoor B., Antibacterial resistance: current problems and possible solutions. *Indian J Med Sci* 2005; 59:120-9.

